

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
INSTITUTE OF NURSING SCIENCES,
SRINIVAS NAGAR, MUKKA, SURATHKAL,
MANGALORE- 574146**

VALUE ADDED COURSE

ON

Menopausal Health

DEPARTMENT OF OBG NURSING

Name of the course: Menopausal Health

Aim of the Course:

The aim of the course is to develop in-depth knowledge and understanding in menopausal health. It further helps the students to develop competency in providing quality care to the menopausal women and her families.

Objectives of the Course

On completion of the module, the student will be able to

1. understand the concept of menopausal health in women.
2. review and analyze the anatomy and physiology of menopause.
3. develop competencies in providing quality care to these women.
4. educate women and families about the problems faced by them.
5. discuss the importance of hormone replacement therapy.

Duration:

Theory: 30 hours

Practical: 20 hours

Evaluation :

Assessment methods:

- Test paper (Objective test, short answers and case scenario and questions) - 30 marks
- Assessment of assignments/skills - 20 mark

The examination will be conducted by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University

Criteria for eligibility to appear for University Exam

- i. 80% attendance in theory
- ii. 100% attendance in practical

Criteria for pass

In order to pass a candidate should obtain at least 50% marks aggregate including internal Assessment and marks obtained from college examination

Award of Certificate/Diploma

Certificate will be awarded by the Institute of Nursing Sciences affiliated to Srinivas University.